

Threat to The Tiger: “India's National Animal” by Dogs

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Introduction

In nine days between 21 April and 29 April 2026, an entire tiger family comprising of a tigress (8-10 years old) and her 4 cubs (15-18 month old) died in Kanha National Park, Madhya Pradesh. Three cubs were found dead while the Tigress and her last surviving cub were rescued, visibly ill. Both the tigress and cub died despite initial signs of recovery. This pushed MP's tiger deaths to 27-30 for 2026. India has 785 tigers in MP as per 2022 census. Disease spillover from dogs is now seen as a major emerging threat to tigers, not just poaching.

Symptoms included severe respiratory distress, lung infection, pneumonic conditions, starvation, central nervous system issues. The viscera samples sent to School of Wildlife Forensic And Health, Jabalpur tested positive for Canine Distemper (CDV) on May 8, 2026. A similar CDV outbreak killed 28 lions in Gir (Gujarat) in the year 2018. CDV outbreak first took place in 2003 in Siberian tiger or Amur tiger in Russia.(1). It also spread among wild animals in India, Nepal and Indonesia. India is going through this virus exactly after 23 years now.

A wildlife crisis:

India's 2022 tiger census recorded an estimated 3,682 wild tigers, approximately 70 % of the global wild tiger population (2). That number, celebrated as a conservation triumph, is now in danger because of CDV. Madhya Pradesh, which holds the country's highest concentration of tigers, recorded 55 tiger deaths in 2025, the highest annual toll since the launch of Project Tiger in 1973.

This year the state has already seen 28 tiger deaths recorded by early May alone. Though not all of those deaths involved CDV. Other factors like electrocution, road and rail accidents, poaching and territorial fights also contributed. The next threat to India's national animal may not come from a trap or a gun but from a virus jumping between dogs and tigers.

About CDV

CDV is a highly contagious viral infection capable of affecting many wild carnivores, including tigers, leopards, lions, fox, jackals, civets, and dholes.

Once it enters the nervous system, it can cause fatal neurological disease, abnormal behaviour, loss of fear, respiratory illness, and immune suppression. For decades, it was a domestic animal problem, but it has now seemed to have spread across India's tiger population.

CDV is now considered a bigger emerging threat than poaching because India's tiger numbers are at a 50-year high, but dog populations have exploded too. CDV is a highly contagious disease of domestic dogs that spills over to wild carnivores through respiratory droplets, saliva and close contact. The tigress likely ate an infected dog, and cubs got it from her. Tigers can also get it when stray dogs feed on tiger kills and leave saliva on the carcass.

Stray and feral dogs near buffer villages are considered one potential source behind the spread of the virus. The virus could spread to tigers who end up hunting and eating the dogs, or even if they eat another carnivore that might have eaten an infected dog.

Symptoms of Canine Distemper in tigers

CDV attacks respiratory, gastrointestinal, and nervous systems. It wipes out immunity so other diseases also take over. CDV looks different in wild tigers than in dogs. Field staff and locals are told to report if they see early stage (1-2 weeks after exposure) symptoms like Nasal discharge, coughing, labored breathing, pneumonia. The Kanha tigress and her cubs had “severe respiratory distress.” Thick ocular discharge, conjunctivitis, eyes seem half-closed. Tiger looks dull, weak, not hunting. The Kanha family was found “starving” and “visibly ill”. Diarrhea, vomiting, dehydration. In late stage neurological signs like muscle twitching, head tilt, seizures, circling, loss of coordination. Abnormal behavior like loss of fear of humans, wandering into villages during daytime, disoriented movement. Partial or complete paralysis especially hind legs It is very hard to spot as the Tigers are secretive. By the time symptoms are obvious, mortality is more than 90% and cubs die fastest. All 4 Kanha cubs died within days of each other.

National Action Plan

After CDV was confirmed in Kanha on May 8, 2026, under the guidelines of National Tiger Conservation Authority (NTCA), Ministry of Environment, Forest & Climate Change Government of India November, 2019 to all tiger-range states, MP Forest Department issued statewide orders to all national parks and tiger reserves to vaccinate dogs in nearby villages. Additionally other nationwide measures included creation of vaccinated dog buffer zones around all 53 tiger reserves, Prevention of dogs from using tiger waterholes, water point fencing and sanitation, prevention of entry of dogs into forests by educating villagers, guides, resort owners, and taxi drivers. It has been made mandatory to test post-mortem samples of all carnivore deaths for CDV.

After confirmation, MP Forest Department launched emergency measures that included Dog vaccination drive targeting 1,000 dogs in villages around Kanha's core/buffer zones. More than 400 dogs vaccinated within 5 days, Sanitizing water sources in forests and near villages, fencing to keep dogs out of forests. Other reserves (Panna, Kuno, Satpura) were made on to alert. Tiger Reserves also started mission-mode dog vaccination. All MP parks directed to vaccinate village dogs.

It is not possible to vaccinate wild tigers. India has 60 million free ranging dogs living around all tiger reserves and hence without, the spillover risk is permanent. But if 70% of dogs around a reserve are vaccinated, the development of "herd immunity" stops the virus from reaching tigers. That is why Kanha launched a war-footing drive for 1,000 dogs. Hence the dog vaccination is the main weapon.

Villagers have been trained to report immediately, if Tiger seen in daylight near village, Tiger

not running from humans/vehicles, staggering, falling, or seizure-like movement and dead dogs or foxes near forest boundary.

Threat to neighboring states

Following the recent deaths at Madhya Pradesh's Kanha Tiger Reserve due to Canine Distemper Virus (CDV) spread of this virus in a state like Maharashtra will be disastrous as venturing of big cats like tigers and leopards close to human settlements is very often. It is a very serious and emerging conservation concern for Maharashtra, especially because the State holds one of India's largest inter-connected populations of tigers and leopards living close to dense human settlements. The increasing overlap between big cats and free-ranging dogs creates an ideal pathway for spillover of CDV.

Conclusions

CDV posed more danger to those species, which are on the verge of extinction. Uncontrolled spreading of this virus will lead to extinction of critically endangered species in our forests. The issue is therefore not only about wildlife disease, it is about landscape ecology, unmanaged dog population, waste management, habitat fragmentation, and the growing compression of wilderness into human space. The modern Anthropocene, sometimes the greatest threat to a tiger is no longer the hunter with a gun but a virus carried silently by the village dog sleeping beside our doorstep. Now the Indian Tiger Mission has shifted focus from "anti-poaching" to "anti-disease". The main concern now is vaccinate the dogs to save the tigers.

References:

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